

EXCEL REPORTING TOOLS FOR GENERATING XML FILES FOR CHEMICAL MONITORING

Guidelines for reporting chemical monitoring residues to EFSA
with specifically customised MS Excel workbooks

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Excel reporting tools are Excel workbooks specifically customised to support the data providers in compiling and reporting chemical monitoring residues data to EFSA. In particular, they generate the XML Files with the correct structure for transmission to EFSA via the DCF (Data Collection Framework) and in line with the [SSD2¹](#) (Standard Sample Description 2) data model.

1.1. Standard Sample Description 2 (SSD2)

The *Chemical monitoring reporting guidance for the Chemical Monitoring data collection* (yearly updated and published on the [EFSA Online Library](#)) provides the general specification on how to follow the SSD2 data model for the harmonised data reporting of Chemical Contaminants, Pesticides, Additives and Veterinary Medicinal Product Residues.

A more detailed description of the SSD2 data model is contained in the original guidance *Standard Sample Description ver. 2.0* (<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3424>)

1.2. XML files

XML (Extensible Markup Language) is the data format required to submit structured data to the EFSA Data Collection Framework.

All the technical details and specifications for the preparation of valid SSD2 XML files for the DCF are contained in *The Guidance on Data Exchange version 2.0* (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3945>).

2. THE REPORTING TOOLS

Two Excel tools for XML creation with chemical monitoring data are currently available:

- Excel tool FLAT for SSD2 data collection
- Excel tool With Methods for SSD2 data collection

2.1. Main functionalities of the Excel reporting tools

- Chemical monitoring data to be reported in structured XML files can be easily prepared in Excel
- All the relevant SSD2 fields are already included in the Excel reporting tools (all the mandatory fields and the optional fields that are relevant for Chemical Monitoring)
- Descriptive comments are present on each header of the Excel spreadsheets giving a first basic support with compilation instructions and cross-referencing the SSD1-SSD2 variable names for an easier migration to the SSD2 data model
- The reporting hierarchies of all the SSD2 controlled terminology catalogues are embedded in the reporting tools
- The valid reportable SSD2 codes can be selected from the validation drop-down lists that are present in every cell related to SSD2 variables with a controlled terminology. Each of these cells can be populated selecting codes from a picking list, entering the values manually but also pasting values from the cells of another worksheet with the option to run the catalogues validation afterwards

¹ [Standard Sample Description ver. 2.0](#) (EFSA, 2013)

- The validation check functionality parses the entire content of the worksheets re-applying the validation criteria in all the cells where the rules were overwritten. Other controls on the omission or incompleteness of mandatory fields are performed.
- The *paramCode* can be retrieved by selecting the names of substances from a specific drop- down list.
- The unique result identifier (*resId*) is automatically generated in the reporting tool with methods (the *resId* can be defined in analogous way concatenating the sample identifiers and the paramcode in the flat tool)

3. REPORTING TOOLS AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF MS EXCEL

The Excel reporting tools are available as compressed archive in ZIP format.

Once downloaded, please save and decompress the ZIP archive locally on your computer before opening the Excel file (i.e. please don't open the Excel file from inside the ZIP archive before the extraction)

3.1. Excel file format

Both the Excel reporting tools FLAT and WITH METHODS are saved as Excel 2003 archives in the format .XLS that still makes possible to develop data workbooks that also include VBA code inside.

The latest Excel releases (from 2007 onwards) save the data workbook in .XLSX format where the last 'X' stands for XML that largely extends the worksheet capability in terms of number of records and columns in a compressed format that doesn't allow VBA code inside the workbooks. The last generation of Excel files with VBA code inside (macros) require to be saved in .XLSM format (Excel file with Macros). This specific file extension makes these archives automatically tagged and recognisable as potentially harmful to the systems and are easily locked by security rules. The choice of the .XLS format for the Excel reporting tools was an attempt to avoid macro security lock as much as possible because theoretically it is not possible to know a priori if an XLS file contains VBA code or not. Recently some macro security locks are recognising XLS as files with macros inside, so in principle the reporting tools could even be saved as XLSM files, but the choice of .XLS format, with smaller data capacity, is also meant to limit the number of records in each tool to an amount that doesn't prevent them to work smoothly (i.e. macros and formulas become easily very slow if the worksheet contain very large number of records).

3.2. Excel file formats and working area limitations

In XLS workbooks, the working area of each worksheet is limited to 65,536 rows and 256 columns (column IV is the last of each worksheet):

In XLSX (and XLSM) workbooks, the working area of each worksheet is extended to 1,048,576 rows and 16,384 columns (column XFD is the last of each worksheet):

3.3. Macro security lock

All the functionalities of the reporting tools are implemented with VBA code. As specified in the previous paragraph, despite the tools are implemented in XLS format, recent systems easily recognise them as workbooks containing macros and potentially harmful so the first time the tool is opened a warning message of “Protected View” can appear on the top of the worksheet as in the next figure. If this happens, please click on the “Enable editing” button.

Continuing to open the tool a second security warning notifies that macros have been disabled. Please select the ‘enable macro’ option.

If the macros are not enabled the tool will lose all the functionalities and cannot create the XML output file. If you don’t succeed enabling the macros or you want to change the macro security preferences, please check the macro security settings of your computer (Clicking on the Macro Security button In the Developer tab you will open the Trust centre where the settings can be changed as well as the trusted locations settings).

Should you get the following type of message of blocked content (red status bar) please take care not to run the tool directly from inside the ZIP archive but extract it first on your computer and then open the Excel workbook. If the problem persists you can try to save the file on a trusted folder of your computer changing the name to the Excel file. If the status bar of blocked content still prevents you to have the macros enabled, this means that your organisation has a specific security policy in place, and you need to ask to the administrator of your computer how to proceed.

BLOCKED CONTENT Macros in this document have been disabled by your enterprise administrator for security reasons.

4. STRUCTURE AND FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE TOOLS

Two types of reporting tools are available as Excel workbook: the XML creation tool FLAT and the tool WITH METHODS. Several functionalities are common to both the tools despite the data reporting schema of the tools is completely different, but they are both aimed to produce the same output: a well-formed XML file with SSD2 structure ready for submission in DCF.

The FLAT tool is conceived for a simpler usage with a straightforward structure of the input: each record includes samples attributes, laboratory information and analytical results on the same line of a database that has the flat structure of an ordinary Excel table. Consequently, some information describing the samples and the analytical methods is redundant in this tool.

The tool WITH METHODS allows to reduce redundancy keeping the input information related to samples, analytical methods and positive detections saved in 3 separated types of worksheets. The result is a much more compact workbook from which the complete database is generated when the XML is written in the output files.

In the next paragraphs the basic functionalities that are common to both the tools are explained. To consider that also the internal validation procedure and the XML creation procedure are common to both the tools, but they will be explained in the next chapter as part of the data preparation.

4.1. Fields description

Not all the SSD2 fields are included in the Excel reporting tools despite they are all reportable. The aim of the reporting tools is to support the reporting needs covered by the “Chemical monitoring reporting guidance: 2020 data collection” where all the relevant fields for the Chemical Monitoring Data Collection are commented and explained in a specific paragraph. The 2020 reporting guidance has been the first one covering the criteria for the harmonization of chemical monitoring across different domains, but the reduced set of SSD2 variables is extended to the years after 2020 and replicated in all the related data collection guidance documents.

The Excel reporting tools include 57 of the 98 SSD2 fields listed in table 4 of the Guidance.

All the 28 mandatory and dependent mandatory fields are included. Other 29 relevant fields with a specific explanation paragraph in the Guidance are included because considered relevant for the Chemical Monitoring data collection.

The content of 31 fields over 57 have to be filled in according to a specific catalogue of controlled terminologies. The data entry is free of control for the rest of the fields

The order of the fields in the Excel reporting tools follows the order of table 4 for an easier reference to the Guidance. Colours, font and special labels in the headers are meant to provide additional support to the user when compiling the data.

4.1.1. Fields of the reporting tool FLAT

The 57 fields are all in the same table (Samples) in the reporting tool FLAT:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
progId	progLegalRef	sampStrategy	progType	sampMethod	sampler	sampPoint	sampEventId	sampUnitType	sampId	sampCountry

L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W		
sampY	sampM	sampD	sampInfo.OrigSampId	sampMatType	sampMatCode	sampMatText	origCountry	origFishAreaCode	analysisY	anMatCode	anPortSeq		
X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD	AE	AF	AG				
labId	labAccred	labCountry	paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId	anMethType	anMethCode	anMethText				
AH	AI	AJ	AK	AL	AM	AN	AO	AP	AQ	AR	AS	AT	AU
resId	accredProc	resUnit	resLOD	resLOQ	CCalpha	CCbeta	resVal	resValRec	resValRecCorr	exprResPerc.moistPerc	exprResPerc.fatPerc	exprResType	resQualValue
AV	AW	AX	AY	AZ	BA	BB	BC	BD	BE				
resType	resValUncert	resInfo.notSummed	evalLowLimit	evalLimitType	evalCode	actTakenCode	evalInfo.conclusion	evalInfo.com	evalInfo.resAsses				

4.1.2. Fields of the reporting tool WITH METHODS

In the reporting tool WITH METHODS the fields are divided in three groups and distributed over three different main types of worksheets:

Samples worksheet

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J		
progId	sampStrategy	progType	sampMethod	sampler	sampPoint	sampEventId	sampUnitType	sampId	sampCountry		
K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V
sampY	sampM	sampD	sampInfo.OrigSampId	sampMatType	sampMatCode	sampMatText	origCountry	origFishAreaCode	analysisY	anMatCode	anPortSeq
W	X	Y	Z								
labId	labAccred	labCountry	MethodSheet								

Not an SSD2 field but selector of methods sheets

Methods worksheets

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
progLegalRef	paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId	anMethType	anMethCode	anMethText	
I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
accredProc	resUnit	resLOD	resLOQ	CCalpha	CCbeta	resQualValue	resType	evalCode

These fields are repeated on purpose (see the explanation later in this document)

Results worksheet

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
sampId	paramCode	paramText	resId	resVal	resValRec	resValRecCorr	exprResPerc.moistPerc	exprResPerc.fatPerc	exprResType	resQualValue
L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	
resType	resValUncert	resInfo.notSummed	evalLowLimit	evalLimitType	evalCode	actTakenCode	evalInfo.conclusion	evalInfo.com	evalInfo.resAsses	

These fields are repeated here on purpose (see the explanation later in this document)

Methods worksheets enhanced (from March 2022)

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H				
progLegalRef	paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId	anMethType	anMethCode	anMethText				
I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
accredProc	resUnit	resLOD	resLOQ	CCalpha	CCbeta	resQualValue	resType	exprResPerc.moistPerc	exprResPerc.fatPerc	exprResType	evalCode

These fields are repeated on purpose (see the explanation later in this document)

Results worksheet

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
sampleId	paramCode	paramText	resId	resVal	resValRec	resValRecCorr	exprResPerc.moistPerc	exprResPerc.fatPerc	exprResType	resQualValue
L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	
resType	resValUncert	resInfo.notSummed	evalLowLimit	evalLimitType	evalCode	actTakenCode	evalInfo.conclusion	evalInfo.com	evalInfo.resAsses	

These fields are repeated here on purpose (see the explanation later in this document)

Note on special fields and on variables that are repeated on both the Results and the Method sheets of the reporting tool WITH METHODS

- The last field of “Samples” (**MethodSheet**) is not an SSD2 field but is meant to specify the methods sheets connected to that sample.
- To note that the **progLegalRef** field has been moved from the Samples worksheet to the Methods despite in SSD2 it was conceived as an attribute of the samples. This is to make possible the reporting of the legal reference at results level.
- The fields **resQualValue**, **resType**, **evalCode**, **exprResType**, **exprResPerc.fatPerc** and **exprResPerc.moistPerc**, are included in both the Methods and the Results worksheet. This is done on purpose to let the user specify them differently depending on if the record contains a non-detected or a positive detection.
- All the above-mentioned fields that are repeated on both the Results and Methods worksheets, if filled in, will be inserted in the XML output file giving the priority to the values inserted in the Results sheet. The values inserted in the Methods sheets will be considered for the output only for negative results (i.e. when a negative result is reported, all the needed data are specified with only the Samples and the related Method sheets, but when a positive detection is reported it is specified in the Results sheet, so it become pointless to specify also in the Method sheet the variables **resQualValue**, **resType**, **evalCode**, **exprResType**, **exprResPerc.fatPerc** and **exprResPerc.moistPerc** .
- **sampleId** and **paramCode** are needed in the Results worksheet in order to create a link among positive detections and laboratory methods.

Headers, colour, and font conventions

- Background colours are meant to evidence the SSD2 section to which each field belongs:

Section_code	Section	Color
A	Local organization	(Not included)
B	Sampling programme	
C	Sampling event	
D	Sample taken	
E	Matrix sampled	
F	Sample analysed	
G	Matrix analysed	
H	Sample analysed portion	
I	Isolate	(Not included)
J	Laboratory	
K	Parameter	
L	Analytical Method	
M	Result	
N	Evaluation	

- Darker background colours and a larger - bold font of the header names are meant to identify the fields that are mandatory or dependent mandatory:

D	E	F	G	H	I	J
progType	sampMethod	sampler	sampPoint	sampEventId	sampUnitType	sampId
Mandatory	Optional	Mandatory	Mandatory	Optional	Optional	Mandatory

The status Mandatory/Optional of each field is also reported in the special labels associated to each column header

4.2. Quick reference labels

An additional support to the user compiling data is a quick reference to the Guidance that can be easily retrieved moving the mouse on the column headers. Each label includes 10 different information:

- SSD2 Code of the field
- SSD2 Element name
- SSD2 Element description
- Name of the controlled terminology catalogue associated with the field (if any)
- Status Mandatory/Optional of the field
- Field format according to the SSD2 structure (string, numbers and their length)
- Cross-reference with the corresponding SSD1 variable

8. Operational notes: a more extended description of the SSD2 variable with some additional hints and references
9. Font colour of the label: a label written in red means that the field is mandatory or dependent mandatory while the blue is used for optional fields
10. Background colour of the labels: soft-blue background means that a controlled terminology has to be respected for that field while a pale-yellow background means that the content of the field is free

Example 1: the FoodEx2 code of the matrix analysed is mandatory (specified in line 5 and red colour) and the data entry has to respect a controlled terminology (specified in line 4 and by the soft-blue background)

Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X
sampMatCode	sa	<p>- SSD2 Code: E.02</p> <p>- SSD2 Element: sampMatCode</p> <p>- Description: Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken</p> <p>- Controlled Terminology: MTX</p> <p>- Reporting is: Mandatory</p> <p>- SSD2 Format: CompoundType</p> <p>- In SSD1 it was: EFSAProdCode, prodProdMeth, prodPack, prodTreat, prodingred</p> <p>- Operational notes: Describes the food or feed product or matrix sampled using the FoodEx2 catalogue. Please select a code from the 'Reporting hierarchy' of the MTX/FoodEx2 catalogue.</p>					

Example 2: the text description of the matrix analysed is optional (specified in line 5 and blue colour) and the data entry is free (empty in line 4 and pale-yellow background)

R	S	T	U	V	W	X
sampMatText	sa	<p>- SSD2 Code: E.03</p> <p>- SSD2 Element: sampMatText</p> <p>- Description: Text description of the matrix of the sample taken</p> <p>- Controlled Terminology:</p> <p>- Reporting is: Optional</p> <p>- SSD2 Format: xs:string (250)</p> <p>- In SSD1 it was: prodText</p> <p>- Operational notes: Describes the characteristics of the sample using free text. Used when suitable codes to describe the item sampled are not found in the FoodEx2 coding.</p>				

4.3. Validation drop down lists and automated rebuild of the validation rules

31 catalogues of the SSD2 controlled terminologies are embedded in the Excel reporting tools and visualised by means of drop-down lists inside all the cells of the related fields. Each drop-down list is performing the double role of guided input for the user and validation rule.

The drop-down lists show in alphabetical order the SSD2 codes of the reporting hierarchy of the catalogue related to each field. (Selecting the terms descriptions from the catalogue and getting the code in the concerned cell would be more user friendly than selecting directly from a list of codes. This solution was considered and identified in first instance during the reporting tools preparation, with the clear objective not to use other special programming objects for drop-down lists than the standard validation functionality of Excel. Being the term to be validated the description and not the code, this solution proven to be helpful only in the unlikely case that all the cells of the worksheet are filled in one by one manually picking names from the drop-down list, so it was abandoned in favour of the lists of codes).

The cells validated by means of controlled terminology can be filled in in three different ways:

1. Scrolling the drop-down list and selecting a code (in each single cell)
2. Inputting the codes manually (in each single cell)
3. Copying-pasting the code(s) from elsewhere (also ranges of cells)

Please note that the reaction of the validation rule in Excel is different for the three type of data input listed above:

1. No reaction as the code is selected from the validation list it is valid by definition
2. No reaction if the code typed in manually is correct.

If a wrong code is typed in manually the validation error message is returned:

3. Copying and pasting values from another source implies temporary by-passing the validation rule. This has pros and cons. The disadvantage is that the validation rule doesn't react, but the advantage is that a massive input can be entered without generating a sequence of error messages at each eventual wrong value pasted in the controlled cells. Moreover, if the copy-paste is applied without specifying "text only" the drop-down list and the validation rules can be completely overridden. For this reason, the Excel reporting tools include a specific validation-check procedure that rebuilds all the time the entire set of validation rules for all the cells in the data worksheet.

4.4. Selection of the chemicals reported

As mentioned, the realisation of dropdown lists based only on the Excel validation functionalities implied listing the SSD codes and not the descriptions of the catalogue terms in the drop-down lists. However, the option to select the analysed chemicals (paramCode) by name and not by code was a clear request of the users, so the functionality could be exceptionally accommodated in the tool using the paramText field as a space to list chemical names that, once selected, are converted in codes in the paramCode cell besides the selected name.

This works also in the opposite direction (selecting a paramCode, the tool automatically returns the name in the paramText column).

4.5. Getting the SSD2 codes translated on the fly

As looking at SSD2 codes is not always meaningful to the users, the reporting tools include a helpful functionality for decoding codes already entered in the cells. A double click on the cells with controlled terminology returns the corresponding catalogue description of the code in that cell, if any.

As double clicking on the cell is the action normally performed to edit a single cell content, please note that this functionality can still be obtained using the key F2.

4.6. Compound fields

The SSD2 data model introduces the possibility to report **compound fields** that are fields where a base term can be specified followed by one or more attributes.

The syntax of XML tags for compound fields is different than for normal fields and it is quite specific. According to the Guidance on data Exchange v.2 (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3945>) and to recent settings of the Data Collection Framework, three different syntax are allowed for compiling compound fields in datasets. Two are the relevant syntax for the reporting tools:

1	< sampMatCode >base#f1=value1\$...\$fn=valuen</ sampMatCode >
2	< sampMatCode.base>value</sampMatcode.base> <sampMatCode.f1>value1</ sampMatCode.f1> <sampMatCode.fn>valuen</sampMatCode.fn>

Considering the essential subset of SSD2 elements included in the Excel reporting tools, the following fields are pre-set as compound for the Chemical Monitoring data collection:

- sampMatCode
- anMatCode
- exprResPerc
- samplInfo
- resInfo
- evallInfo

In order to include compound fields in the reporting tools using the simplest format for the users they have been 'parametrized', except the fields that have the FoodEx2 as controlled terminology (MTX catalogue) where it is not practical to parametrize the facets and all the possible combinations.

The parametrization is meant to put a constraint on the only attribute reportable and accepted by the Chemical Monitoring Data Collection. Using the second syntax listed above, the XML generated by the tools includes the following compound fields names in the tags:

- **exprResPerc.moistPerc**
- **exprResPerc.fatPerc**
- **sampInfo.OrigSampleId**
- **resInfo.notSummed**
- **evalInfo.conclusion**
- **evalInfo.com**
- **evalInfo.resAsses**

Therefore, the above syntax is used for the names of the related Excel reporting tools headers.

As mentioned, exception is done for the FoodEx2 related fields sampMatCode and anMatCode that have to be reported as strings, specifying the facets using the first syntax listed above and the conventional separators: \$ and #

- **sampMatCode**
- **anMatCode**

4.7. Repeatable fields

The SSD2 data model introduces the possibility to report **repeatable fields** where more than one term can be specified for the same variable. The syntax of XML is a string with the sequence of one or more catalogue terms separated by a "\$" character without trailing spaces. The repeatable fields in the ChemMon data collection are two: progLegalRef and actTakenCode.

For each of these fields the sequential selection of a series of terms from the drop-down list triggers the automated append and concatenation of each term to the string in the cell. The "\$" separator is added automatically after each selected term, and an internal check is performed in order to avoid that the same term is repeated more than once (e.g. N027A\$N129A\$N112A for progLegalRef or B\$D\$G\$A for actTakenCode).

The automated concatenation of sequential drop-down choices in these two fields has been introduced in the release 2.0 of the reporting tools while in the first release a list of strings with the pre-set combinations of a limited number of base terms was stored as an extension of the original catalogue and listed in the validation drop-down list.

The sequential concatenation produced by the repeated choice in the drop-down list creates strings that are not elements of the SSD catalogues used by the Excel validation, that would result in a number of error reported after the validation check. For this reason, for cells containing repeated terms, the validation check will not report an error, but just suggests checking these cells manually.

The repeatable fields can also be compiled typing in the concatenated string directly or copying and pasting, as for all the other fields (see paragraph 4.4).

5. COMPILING AND EXPORTING DATA WITH THE REPORTING TOOLS

5.1. The reporting tool “FLAT”

The data entry area of the FLAT tool is implemented as a simple Excel table (flat structure) with the all the mandatory and relevant SSD2 variables as columns. The FLAT reporting tool consists of three worksheets:

- **Samples:** the worksheet compiled with all the data to be converted in XML format
- **VALIDATION CHECK:** a console for running the validation procedure that checks if the controlled terminology catalogues are correctly applied in the Samples worksheet and returns a list of cells that failed the control.
- **RUN_XML_CREATION:** a console to run the code that automatically generates the XML file and returns the feedback on the files created.

5.1.1. Data compilation with the reporting tool “FLAT”

The **Samples** worksheet is used for the compilation of data describing the samples and all the analytical results related to each.

The user has to fill in the Samples worksheet following the proposed table structure in order to get a valid XML. Eliminating or adding columns in the Samples worksheet will prevent the creation of a valid XML. Each record of this table corresponds to an analytical result reported. The information related to the sample descriptors has to be repeated for each result belonging to the same sample (blue blocks in the figure below). The laboratory parameters referred to a substance or group of substances analysed with the same method are repeated for each sample where the same analytical method applies (green blocks in the figure). Green blocks that don't extend in the orange “Results” columns are all the non-detected results of the dataset. Positive detections are reported in single lines that are like “extension” of the corresponding lines in the green blocks of analytical methods descriptors.

SAMPLE 1	METHOD 1	
SAMPLE 2	METHOD 2	RESULT 1
	METHOD 3	RESULT2
		RESULT3
SAMPLE 3	METHOD 1	
	METHOD 2	
	METHOD 1	

5.1.2. Unique result identifier (resID) in the tool FLAT

While in the Excel reporting tool with methods the resID is generated automatically, in the FLAT tool the resID needs to be compiled by the user. The unique result identifier (resID) is a mandatory field that can't be applied to more than one record in the data collection. The resID is very important when a single analytical result has to be referred in the entire ChemMon data collection (i.e. in the EFSA Data Warehouse or in case of amendment to a dataset in the DCF).

In lack of a unique identifier of the results directly available from the laboratory data at national level the recommendation is to generate it inserting in the resID the Excel formula that concatenates the sample identifier and the paramCode of each result: **=sampleID¶mCode** (in line with the automatic resID generation in the tool with methods).

5.2. The reporting tool "WITH METHODS"

The data entry space of the tool WITH METHODS is composed by a set of three types of Excel tables aiming at the reduction of data input by the data providers minimising redundant information. All the mandatory and relevant SSD2 variables are included as columns of the three types of Excel worksheets the union of which generates the entire set of analytical results at the end of the XML creation

The tool WITH METHODS consists of five different types of worksheets:

RUN_XML_CREATION	VALIDATION CHECK	Samples	Method_01	Method_02	Method_N	Results
------------------	------------------	---------	-----------	-----------	----------	---------

- **Samples:** for reporting information at sample level. All the samples reported are listed and described in this worksheet
- **Methods:** for reporting the descriptors of a single laboratory method. This type of worksheet will be replicated as many times as the laboratory methods reported. The Reporting Tool with Methods is delivered with three empty method worksheets as examples.
- **Results:** for reporting positive detections. Each positive result reported in this table has to be linked to a sample and to a specific substance reported in one of the laboratory methods sheets.

- **VALIDATION CHECK:** a console for running the validation procedure that checks if the controlled terminology catalogues are correctly applied in the Samples worksheet and returns a list of cells that failed the control.
- **RUN_XML_CREATION:** a console to run the code that automatically generates the XML file and returns the feedback on the files created.

5.2.1. Data compilation with the reporting tool “WITH METHODS”

The data compilation is distributed among the **Samples**, **Methods** and **Results** worksheets.

- **Samples:** all the samples reported are listed and described in this worksheet with a unique sample identifier and all the descriptors at sample level according to the SSD2 data model. The last column of this worksheet (“MethodSheet”) is not an SSD2 field but a list of the Method names referred to the Method sheets available in the workbook and containing information on the substances analysed in that sample. The sample information is repeated for the same sample as many times as the number of analytical methods that apply to that sample.
- **Methods:** The tool WITH METHODS is provided with three empty models of the Method worksheet (named “Method_01”, “Method_02”, “Method_N”). The data provider will make copies of the empty Method sheets according to the amount of laboratory methods reported. Each new copy of the Method sheet will be renamed, ideally with a meaningful method name. There are no constraints for the names of the Method worksheets. The drop-down list in the last column of the Samples worksheet ensures the correct choice and entry of method names related to each sample. The compilation of data in the Methods worksheets is specific to each method reported.
- Please note that specifying the analytical parameters in one of the Method sheets is mandatory for all the substances analysed, either if non-detected or positive results.
- Negative results of screening methods (e.g. Delvotest for milk) can be fully described and reported in the Methods sheets. This is the reason for including the result type descriptors and the related evaluation (resQualValue, resType, evalCode) in both the Results sheet and in the Methods sheets.
- **Results:** only positive detections with occurrence quantification, legal limits and evaluation of the analytical results are listed here. The result evaluation of non-detections (not listed in the Results worksheet) has to be provided in the concerned Method sheet following the given structure to enable the export to XML. The paramCode of a positive detection cannot be present only in the Results worksheet, but it must be reported also in the related Method sheet otherwise the XML output will not be able to include and fully describe the substances analysed. A specific validation check is included in the tool for the identification of “orphan” paramCodes reported in the Results worksheet without having a correspondence in any of the Methods sheets.

The sample descriptors are repeated once for each analytical method applied to the sample. The laboratory parameters of an analytical method are compiled only once and separately in the related Method worksheet (that is good practice to rename accordingly). The analytical parameters described in each Methods sheet

may be extended in the Results worksheet in case of positive detections with occurrence quantification, legal limits and evaluation of the results. Alternatively, for non-detections, the type and evaluation of result has to be specified in each of the Methods sheets according to the selectable terms in the drop-down lists of the specific fields: resQualValue, resType, evalCode. Whenever a result is positive (record 'extended' to the Results sheet) the tool will automatically consider the resQualValue, resType and evalCode compiled in the Results worksheet disregarding what is selected in the corresponding fields of the related Method sheet.

5.2.2. Unique result identifier (resID) in the tool WITH METHODS

The unique result identifier (resID) is a mandatory field that become even more important when a single analytical result has to be referred in the entire ChemMon data collection (i.e. in the EFSA Data Warehouse or in case of amendment to a dataset in the DCF).

In the Excel reporting tool with methods the resID is also the key for merging positive detections reported in the Results worksheet with the related sample and laboratory information. A mistake in the resID would cause a positive detection to be lost in the phase of XML creation. For this reason, in the Excel reporting tool with methods the resID is automatically generated by the tool concatenating the sampID and paramCode fields: **sampID¶mCode**.

In the Method worksheets the tool will generate the resID concatenating each paramCode with the sampID of the sample to which that method is applied. This is not visible to the user because the resID field is not included in the Method worksheets.

In the Results worksheet the tool will generate the resID concatenating each sampID and paramCode reported in the first two columns.

The user doesn't need to compile this field, but if considered useful this formula can be used anyway in the resID field of the Results worksheet. It has to be taken into consideration that whatever is written in the resID column of the Results worksheet will be overwritten by the tool when a validation check is launched or when the XML output is created.

5.3. Validation check of the compiled data

The main function of the reporting tools is to provide support for entering data according to the SSD2 schema and prepare well-formed XML files for transmission to the EFSA Data Collection Framework. Even if a complete pre-validation of data (i.e. checking with all the business rules) is out of the scope, a number of validations are implemented in the reporting tools for supporting the user to perform a first terminology check before submitting the file to the DCF.

The validation of the controlled terminologies is implemented in the tools based on the standard Excel validation functionalities. All the SSD2 catalogues are embedded in the reporting tools and used to generate the Excel validation drop-down lists in all the concerned cells. However, the Excel validation rules work only when data are selected directly from the drop-down lists or entered manually in the cells (i.e. an error is returned in case of wrong terms manually written in the cell). As the copy-paste operation is one of the possible methods to enter data in the Excel reporting tools, the validation rules are skipped, and the related drop-down lists are easily overridden. In order to solve this issue a functionality is needed to rebuild all the validation lists that for some reasons have been lost or corrupted and to re-apply the validation rules to all the cells. This functionality is provided in the VALIDATION CHECK worksheet together with other useful controls on the data.

The VALIDATION CHECK worksheet includes a button for launching the validation check procedure and several areas where the validation outputs are reported. The following figure shows all the elements of the VALIDATION CHECK. The output areas are empty because there are no errors found to list.

The validation check procedure performs the following operations and controls on all the data worksheets (Samples, Methods and Results):

- regenerates all the column headers in case some were inadvertently overridden or modified
- rebuilds all the validation rules and drop-down lists in all the concerned cells
- checks all the cells for violations of the validation rules
- checks all the cells where allowed repeated terms are used (progLegalRef and actTakenCode)
- count the total number of catalogue violations and prints it in red in the area [6]
- count the total number of repeated terms reported and prints it in yellow in the area [6]
- prints a list of cells with violations (in red) and with repeated terms to be checked manually (in yellow) for each of the worksheets in separate columns - area [7]
- creates all the resID strings in the Results worksheet concatenating sampID and paramCode
- checks if one or more worksheet are empty and prints a list of empty sheets in area [3]
- checks all the mandatory fields that are fully or partially omitted and creates a list in area [5]
- checks in the Results worksheet if some of the paramCodes reported are not related to a specific method sheet ("lost" paramCodes) and creates a list in area [4] if any
-

In the next figure a scenario with different types of compilation mistakes is simulated and the output area are showing several error messages.

CHECK DATA VALIDATION

CHECK VALIDATION

All the variables for which a controlled terminology exists are controlled as well as mandatory fields incomplete or fully omitted

CONTROLLED TERMINOLOGY UPDATE

LAST UPDATE: 04/04/2020 18:12:41

Worksheet(s) not validated because empty:

[Meth_Acetamidrid],

n. 5 paramCodes in the Results worksheet are not found in any of the Methods worksheet.
 - RF-00005727-PAR - RF-00005759-PAR - RF-0014-001-PPP - RF-0150-001-PPP - RF-0373-001-P

MANDATORY fields FULLY OMITTED [n.1 in Samples]: sampY, [n.4 in Meth_MULTI]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText, [n.3 in Meth_Dithiocarbammates]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText, [n.3 in Meth_Dithiocarbammates]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText, [n.3 in Meth_Dithiocarbammates]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText

MANDATORY fields INCOMPLETE: [n.4 in Samples]: sampler, sampPoint, sampY, sampMatCode, [n.4 in Meth_MULTI]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText, [n.3 in Meth_Dithiocarbammates]: anMethRefid, anMethType, anMethCode, anMethText

Violation of the controlled terminologies in the SAMPLES worksheet are listed below --> TOTAL 23 CELLS VIOLATING THE CATALOGUE VALIDATION - Please select the correct terms!

(double click on each position to jump directly to the related cells)

Samples	Meth_MULTI	Meth_Dithiocarbammates	Meth_Mepiquat	Meth_Fosetyl	Results
C3	H4	D2			K3
E3	A7	E2			K7
S3	G9				
B4	A16				
S4					
B5					
D5					
B6					
C6					
E7					
C8					
D8					
D10					
B11					
E12					

← ... VALIDATION CHECK
Samples
Meth_MULTI
Meth_Dithiocarbammates
Meth_Acetamidrid
Meth_Mepiquat
Meth_Fosetyl
Results
... +

Each cell in the list of violations of controlled terminology (area [7]) contains the address of a cell in the corresponding data worksheet where a catalogue violation was found. The user can double-click in each of the cells listed in [7] in order to jump directly to the cell for visualizing and fixing the error.

The sequential concatenations produced by the choices in the drop-down list of repeatable fields (progLegalRef and actTakencode) creates strings in the cells that are different from the catalogue terminology used by the Excel validation, so it would result in a number of wrong cells evidenced in red after the validation check, but not necessarily these are mistakes. For this reason, in case of repeated terms, the validation check will skip the Excel validation and it will just suggest checking these cells manually. The cells containing repeated terms are marked in yellow (instead than red) by the validation check.

Incomplete mandatory fields are not marked with colours in the data worksheet but are listed separately for each worksheet in area [5]. To note that, upon request from some data providers, the 'dependent-mandatory' fields are no longer counted among the omitted or partially omitted mandatory fields as it was the case in the first release of the reporting tools.

Some examples are reported in the next figures:

Violation of the controlled terminologies in the SAMPLES worksheet are listed below
 (double click on each position to jump directly to the related cells)

Samples	Meth_MULTI	Meth_Dithiocarba	Meth_Mepiquat	Meth_Fosety
C3	H4	D2		
E3	A7	E2		
S3	G9			
B4	A16			
S4				
B5				

Double-click here
to jump here

sampStrategy	progType	sampMethod	sampler	sampPoint
ST10A	K005A	N009A	CX02A	E100A
ST19A	K005A	N045A		E100A
ST20A	K005A	N009A		E100A
ST20A	K055A	N009A		E100A
ST19A	K005A	N009A		E100A
ST10A	K005A	N045A		E100A
ST19A	K055A	N009A	CX02A	E100A
ST10A	K005A	N009A	CX02A	E100A
ST10A	K055A	N009A	CX02A	E100A
ST10A	K005A	N009A	CX02A	E100A
ST10A	K005A	N045A	CX02A	E100A
ST20A	K005A	N009A	CX02A	E100A

Incomplete mandatory fields
Listed here

MANDATORY fields FULLY OMITTED [n.1 in Samples]: sampY, [n.4 in Meth_MULTI]: anMethRefId, anM
MANDATORY fields INCOMPLETE: [n.4 in Samples]: sampler, sampPoint, sampY, sampMatCode, [n.4

Some repeatable fields are reported by the validation check suggesting manual check:

Violation of the controlled terminologies in the SAMPLES worksheet are listed below (double click on the cell addresses listed below for jumping directly to the related cells)		--> TOTAL 1 CELLS VIOLATING THE CATALOGUE VALIDATION! (double click on RED CELLS)
		--> TOTAL 3 CELLS TO VERIFY IN REPEATABLE FIELDS (double click on YELLOW CELLS)
Samples		
B3		
B5		
B8		
B9		

progId	progLegalRef	sampStrategy	progType
5078	N252A	ST10A	K009A
5078	N023A\$N304A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N252A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N023A\$N112A\$N017A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N252A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N252A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N023A	K005A	K005A
5078	N252A\$ST10A	ST10A	K005A
5078	N252A	ST10A	K005A

The validation check procedure can be launched at any time. It is strongly recommended to run it during the data compilation in order to have the controlled terminology drop-down always updated and to identify the possible mistakes during the data compilation, in particular before running the XML creation procedure.

5.4. XML creation with the reporting tools

The last step performed with the reporting tools by the data providers before transmitting data to EFSA is the export of all the data compiled in XML format. This functionality is provided in the RUN_XML_CREATION worksheet.

Once the data tables are completed in the reporting tools and ready for transferring the data to the XML files, the data provider has to click the grey button in the RUN_XML_CREATION worksheet and select 'yes' to confirm the XML creation.

RUN XML CREATION

< RUN XML >

Please run a **VALIDATION CONTROL** before creating the XML
Omitted or incomplete mandatory variables cause data rejection

CONTROLLED TERMINOLOGY UPDATE
LAST UPDATE: 04/04/2020 18:12:41

XML output files are saved in the same folder as the input files with the name(s) **AnalyticalMeasure(n).XML** according to the split applied by the tool

XML creation run
? RUNNING THE XML CREATION, DO YOU CONFIRM?
Si No

N. 1 XML files were created (listed below) - click on the number on the left to view them in their folder

- 1 C:\Myfolder\AnalyticalMeasure1.xml
- 2 C:\Myfolder\AnalyticalMeasure2.xml
- 3 C:\Myfolder\AnalyticalMeasure3.xml

The automatic split of the dataset creates a multitude of XML files

Click here to open the output folder

The Excel reporting tools automatically split the dataset inserted in the workbooks and creates XML files of suitable size for the upload to the DCF (i.e. max 20.000 records per file). If only one XML is created, it is named by default 'AnalyticalMeasure1' and saved in the same folder of the Excel tool.

If more than one XML are generated (due to the high number of records) the next output files will have all the same name, followed by a progressive numbering (e.g. 'AnalyticalMeasure1', 'AnalyticalMeasure2', 'AnalyticalMeasure3', etc.)

For this reason, it is suggested to modify the default names of the XML files with more meaningful names, possibly referred to the content of the file.

Please note that the output of the validation check doesn't affect at all the creation of the XML output. Should you get error messages from the validation check, please evaluate them in order to comply with the catalogue terminologies and fields completeness. Anyway, the XML can be created even without fixing the errors reported by the validation check. The same errors will be then identified by the DCF validation process once the XML will be uploaded.